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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF TRADITIONAL VS. FUNCTIONAL GRAMMAR
APPROACHES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING IN UZBEKISTAN

Muyassar Komiljon qizi Jumabayeva

An intern teacher at Alfraganus University in Tashkent city.

E-mail: muyassar0900@icloud.com

Phone number: (88) 496-60-05.

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Abstract. *The teaching of foreign languages, particularly English, has gained strategic importance in the Uzbek education system in recent years. Foreign language, especially English, remains the key to success in International Communication, Science, Technology and business. In the implementation of these goals, it is important to choose a grammar teaching methodology. This article will analyze traditional and functional grammar approaches and highlight their advantages and disadvantages, as well as draw conclusions about which approach is more effective in the Uzbek context.*

Keywords: *English teaching, traditional grammar, functional grammar, communicative methodology, Uzbek educational system, grammar rules.*

СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ТРАДИЦИОННЫХ И ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ
ПОДХОДОВ К ГРАММАТИКЕ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА В
УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

Аннотация. *Преподавание иностранных языков, в частности английского, приобрело стратегическое значение в узбекской системе образования в последние годы.*

Иностранный язык, особенно английский, остается ключом к успеху в международной коммуникации, науке, технологиях и бизнесе. При реализации этих целей важно выбрать методику преподавания грамматики. В этой статье будут проанализированы традиционные и функциональные подходы к грамматике и выделены их преимущества и недостатки, а также сделаны выводы о том, какой подход более эффективен в узбекском контексте.

Ключевые слова: *преподавание английского языка, традиционная грамматика, функциональная грамматика, коммуникативная методика, узбекская образовательная система, правила грамматики.*

Nowadays, the importance of learning English is becoming much higher in Uzbekistan than before. A few English experts are bringing to life new methods and ways to learn English.

Noyabr, 2024-Yil

This will certainly further increase the effectiveness of teaching foreign languages. There are several specific advantages to teaching using technology. In addition, it greatly increases the effectiveness of the teaching system and, in turn, promotes the advancement of a language learner by keeping pace with the Times. Technology is slowly taking the place of traditional teaching.

Today, several new programs and shows that help teach English are regularly broadcast on television.

It should also be noted that to improve the effectiveness of teaching today, new methods of using new modern innovative technologies have been introduced in Uzbekistan. For example, a student who is taught a foreign language on a multimedia basis can develop four skills, learn both by sight and by ear through interesting materials. In addition, the reader can guess the meaning of some words by seeing live action and try to get it down.

Some teachers' use of technology during English classes ignorance and lack of use, leading to some boredom of students comes. It is for this reason that the lesson is not to quench the student's passion the use of technologies and at least a computer during the learner's further ensures increased interest.

Traditional grammar approach.

The traditional grammar approach has been a key method in Language Teaching for many years. This approach is based on the study of grammatical rules and their strengthening through practical examples.

Features:

1. It is based on rules and structures: in the traditional approach, the structure of the language is taught within strict rules and grammar rules.
2. Exercises and repetitions: students memorize the rules by performing many exercises.
3. Theory and Practice Division: theoretical rules are taught at the first stage, and later their practical application.

Advantages:

- Relatively easy to understand due to strict rules.
- Students are used to composing grammatically correct sentences.
- Adapts well to Test systems because specific answers are required.

Disadvantages:

- The ability to learn language as a means of communication is limited.
- Students are often unable to apply them in oral or written speech, even if they know the rules of grammar.

- May not be compatible with modern communicative approaches.

Functional grammar approach.

The functional grammar approach, on the other hand, focuses on teaching language as a natural communication tool. An important place in this approach is the understanding of how grammar is used in communication.

Features:

1. Goal-oriented communication: teaches how language rules are used in situations in everyday life.
2. Context-based teaching: grammar is often explained through texts, conversations, or real-life situations.
3. Integration: grammar is taught in conjunction with other language skills (reading, writing, hearing and speaking).

Advantages:

- Students learn how to apply language in real-world situations.
- Develops communicative competence.
- The process of learning the language will be more interesting.

Disadvantages:

- Due to the low emphasis on grammar theory, students may not be able to memorize the rules correctly.
- It will be more difficult to control and evaluate.
- Teachers require a high level of creativity and language competence.

In Uzbekistan's education system, the traditional approach is prioritized in many schools and universities. However, in recent years, elements of a functional approach based on foreign grants and projects are also being introduced. For example, the development of textbooks based on "CEFR" standards and the increased emphasis on communicative methodology in language courses are examples of this.

➤ But, it is important to maintain an ideal balance between traditional and functional approaches. The following recommendations can be useful in this regard:

- Integrated approach: teaching traditional rules should be accompanied by a functional approach.
- Teacher training: it is necessary to improve the skills of educators on a functional approach.
- Updating textbooks: it is important to bring text and exercises closer to real life.

Noyabr, 2024-Yil

In conclusion, it can be said that the use of a combination of them can be effective in teaching English in Uzbekistan, rather than preferring one of the traditional and functional approaches. While the traditional approach helps to strengthen grammatical knowledge, the functional approach teaches the application of this knowledge in real communication. The modern educational process requires teachers and students not to be limited to just one method. For this reason, it is possible to achieve even higher results in teaching English by reconciling both approaches.

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